

A Preliminary Inventory of the Leafhoppers (Cicadellidae) of Nantucket Island

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Abstract

Leafhoppers have not been surveyed on Nantucket Island since a list published by Johnson in 1930, which comprises 54 species. Given that leafhopper diversity in New England totals several hundred species, we expected that the true diversity on Nantucket greatly exceeds the 1930 list. We inventoried leafhoppers on Nantucket for four days in mid-July 2018 to expand on Johnson's checklist. We collected 1,212 leafhoppers from 20 sites across the island. Sorting and identification of specimens is in the early stages, but over half of the taxa identified thus far are new additions to the list of leafhoppers on Nantucket. We anticipate that further identifications will continue to add new species at a similar rate, likely yielding dozens of new additions to the island's known biodiversity.

Introduction

Leafhoppers (Cicadellidae) are small, often-colorful, sap-feeding hemipteran insects that can be found in almost any habitat with vascular plants. Over 20,000 species of leafhoppers have been described worldwide (with perhaps four times as many undescribed species!), and ~3,000 species have been recorded in North America (Dietrich 2005, 2008). Leafhopper diversity on Nantucket has not been formally catalogued since Johnson's (1930) list of Nantucket insect fauna. His list included 55 species of leafhopper at the time, but current taxonomic treatment of those taxa puts his list at 54 species (Table 1). With two additional species posted on BugGuide.net, the current documented checklist for leafhoppers on Nantucket stands at 56 species, to the best of our knowledge. However, it is likely that the island is home to many more

species than this, considering that a recently published checklist for New Hampshire includes 605 species (Chandler & Hamilton 2017) and at least 10 taxa in the BugGuide or iNaturalist databases from Martha's Vineyard would be new for the Nantucket list.

Collecting leafhoppers is relatively straightforward, but identification to species can sometimes be challenging. The most common method for collecting leafhoppers is to use sweep nets on vegetation, then transfer any captured leafhoppers into vials for later preservation. Leafhoppers are attracted to lights and can also be collected from a sheet illuminated by a bright light source at night. Additional methods for collecting include beating denser vegetation and collecting whatever falls onto a sheet placed underneath. These collection methods can be performed by amateur collectors without specialized equipment, making leafhoppers an excellent subject for local inventories. Identifying collected specimens for such an inventory may take more expertise, however. Many species are quite distinct and can be identified by external morphology, but some require examination of the dissected male genitalia under high magnification. Assuming a collector can perform the necessary dissection, many identification keys are available that will allow them to then make a species determination.

Given the likelihood of greatly expanding the known leafhopper diversity on Nantucket and the relative ease of conducting a leafhopper inventory, we sought to pursue such a project on a preliminary level with the help of a Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative grant. We visited the island for four days in mid-July 2018, collecting adult and nymph leafhoppers with sweep nets across a wide variety of habitats. This inventory is considered preliminary because leafhopper phenology and behavior varies among species, so visits at additional dates using additional collecting methods are required to finish a more complete inventory.

Methods and Study Sites

We collected adult and nymph leafhoppers at 20 sites across Nantucket Island, during 12–15 July 2018 (Table 2). Survey sites were chosen based on maximizing the habitat diversity inventoried and on accessibility by car. We sampled all but one site (20 Vesper Lane) once during daylight hours by using sweep nets on all types of vegetation at a site, and we collected nocturnally once each at the 20 Vesper Lane and U. Mass. Field Station sites using a white sheet illuminated with incandescent and/or CFL bulbs. We anticipated collecting nocturnally with a

UV light as well and at more remote locations, but we could not locate the necessary equipment at the Nantucket Field Station that we thought would be available to us.

When leafhoppers were found in the net or on the sheet, a collector aspirated the leafhoppers into a small glass vial, and all leafhoppers from a given site were transferred to a single vial filled with 100% ethanol for preservation. We are currently using a variety of online and print resources for identifying the adult leafhoppers under a dissecting microscope. Taxa which require examination of male genitalia for species-level identification will likely be sent to Dr. Christopher Dietrich or another expert, and we will need to send the nymphs to experts for identification as well. Alternatively, if we have multiple individuals of an unknown species, we will sequence the DNA barcode for one to identify it.

Results

We collected a total of 1,212 leafhoppers (836 adults, 376 nymphs) from 20 sites on Nantucket Island (Table 2). The total number of individuals collected per site ranged from 2 (20 Vesper Lane) to 219 (Madequecham). We anticipated sorting and identifying specimens during the fall academic semester, but that process was delayed until the current spring semester. Identification is therefore in the very early stages, but we have tentatively identified adults of at least 5 subfamilies, 7 tribes, and 10 genera from 8 locations thus far (Table 3). Notably, 6 of the 10 taxa identified are new additions to the leafhopper checklist for Nantucket.

Discussion

As anticipated, leafhopper diversity on Nantucket clearly exceeds the 54 species listed by Johnson in 1930. We have currently identified only a small sample of the 1,212 individuals we collected during our inventory, but 60% of the taxa identified are not included in Johnson's list. If that ratio remains consistent as we proceed with identifications, we will likely add dozens of species to the Nantucket leafhopper checklist.

Identification of adult specimens has progressed at a slower rate than we anticipated, primarily because extenuating circumstances prevented the process from starting until the Spring 2019 semester. However, we are now working at a slow but steady pace at sorting and identifying adults, and we expect the work rate to increase significantly (and then finish) during the summer. We will proceed with identifying nymphs as much as possible after completion of

the adults. The large number of specimens collected makes the identification stage of the project a bit daunting, but we will get there!

Although we were successful at collecting a large number of specimens, the lack of the anticipated nocturnal collecting equipment likely significantly reduced the number of species we collected. Several expected species that commonly come to collecting sheets at night (on the mainland, at least) were not found during our sweep netting efforts. We predict that additional inventories that utilize nocturnal collecting will discover many species that we did not observe. Inventories conducted at different times of the summer and fall would also be likely to record many species that we did not, given that leafhopper adult phenology varies among species. Thus, while we consider our preliminary inventory to have been successful, we are confident that future inventories are necessary to improve the estimate of leafhopper diversity on Nantucket.

Acknowledgments

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Literature Cited

- Chandler, D.S., and K.G.A. Hamilton. 2017. Biodiversity and ecology of the leafhoppers (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae) of New Hampshire. *Transactions of the American Entomological Society* 143:773–971.
- Dietrich, C.H. 2005. Keys to the families of Cicadomorpha and subfamilies and tribes of Cicadellidae (Hemiptera: Auchenorrhyncha). *Florida Entomologist* 88:502–517.
- Dietrich, C.H. 2008. Leafhopper FAQs. Retrieved from <http://wwn.inhs.illinois.edu/~dietrich/lfhFAQ.html>.
- Johnson, C.W. 1930. A list of the insect fauna of Nantucket, Massachusetts. *The Nantucket Maria Mitchell Association* 3:1–159.

Tables and Figures

Table 1. The pre-inventory list of leafhopper species documented on Nantucket Island, primarily based on Johnson (1930), with the two species not listed in Johnson being from BugGuide.net.

As Listed in Johnson (1930)		Subfamily	Current Taxonomy	
Genus	Species		Genus	Species
<i>Cicadella</i>	<i>gothica</i>	Cicadellinae	<i>Amphigonalia</i>	<i>gothica</i>
<i>Draeculacephala</i>	<i>minor</i>	Cicadellinae	<i>Draeculacephala</i>	<i>producta</i>
<i>Draeculacephala</i>	<i>mollipes</i>	Cicadellinae	<i>Draeculacephala</i>	<i>mollipes</i>
<i>Graphocephala</i>	<i>coccinea</i>	Cicadellinae	<i>Graphocephala</i>	<i>coccinea</i>
<i>Graphocephala</i>	<i>coccinea</i> var. <i>teliformis</i>	Cicadellinae	<i>Graphocephala</i>	<i>teliformis</i>
<i>Helochara</i>	<i>communis</i>	Cicadellinae	<i>Helochara</i>	<i>communis</i>
		Cicadellinae	<i>Neokolla</i>	<i>hieroglyphica</i>
<i>Acucephalus</i>	<i>albifrons</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Anoscopus</i>	<i>albifrons</i>
<i>Acucephalus</i>	<i>nervosus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Aphrodes</i>	<i>bicinctus</i>
<i>Balclutha</i>	<i>impicta</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Balclutha</i>	<i>impicta</i>
<i>Balclutha</i>	<i>osborni</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Balclutha</i>	<i>impicta</i>
<i>Chlorotettix</i>	<i>unicolor</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Chlorotettix</i>	<i>unicolor</i>
<i>Cicadula</i>	<i>divisa</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Macrosteles</i>	<i>divisus</i>
<i>Cicadula</i>	<i>sexnotata</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Macrosteles</i>	<i>sexnotatus</i>
<i>Deltocephalus</i>	<i>inimicus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Endria</i>	<i>inimicus</i>
<i>Deltocephalus</i>	<i>littoralis</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Amplicephalus</i>	<i>littoralis</i>
<i>Deltocephalus</i>	<i>obtectus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Polyamia</i>	<i>obtecta</i>
<i>Deltocephalus</i>	<i>sandersi</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Flexamia</i>	<i>sandersi</i>
<i>Euscelis</i>	<i>anthracinus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Limotettix</i>	<i>anthracinus</i>
<i>Euscelis</i>	<i>arctostaphyli</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Limotettix</i>	<i>arctostaphyli</i>
<i>Euscelis</i>	<i>deceptus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Streptanus</i>	<i>relativus</i>
<i>Euscelis</i>	<i>extrusus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Extrusanus</i>	<i>extrusus</i>
<i>Euscelis</i>	<i>relativus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Streptanus</i>	<i>relativus</i>
<i>Euscelis</i>	<i>vaccinii</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Limotettix</i>	<i>vaccinii</i>
<i>Eutettix</i>	<i>cinctus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Menosoma</i>	<i>cincta</i>
<i>Gypona</i>	<i>octolineata</i> var. <i>striata</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Gyponana</i>	<i>striata</i>
<i>Hecalus</i>	<i>lineatus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Neohecalus</i>	<i>lineatus</i>
<i>Ophiola</i>	<i>osborni</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Limotettix</i>	<i>osborni</i>
<i>Ophiola</i>	<i>striatula</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Ophiola</i>	<i>russeola</i>
<i>Penthimia</i>	<i>americana</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Penthimia</i>	<i>americana</i>
<i>Phlepsius</i>	<i>fuscipennis</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Paraphlepsius</i>	<i>fuscipennis</i>
<i>Phlepsius</i>	<i>irroratus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Paraphlepsius</i>	<i>irroratus</i>
<i>Platymetopius</i>	<i>acutus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Scaphytopius</i>	<i>acutus</i>
<i>Platymetopius</i>	<i>angustatus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Scaphytopius</i>	<i>angustatus</i>
<i>Platymetopius</i>	<i>fulvus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Scaphytopius</i>	<i>fulvus</i>
<i>Platymetopius</i>	<i>magdalensis</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Scaphytopius</i>	<i>magdalensis</i>
<i>Scaphoideus</i>	<i>auronitens</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Osbornellus</i>	<i>auronitens</i>
<i>Scaphoideus</i>	<i>immistus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Scaphoideus</i>	<i>immistus</i>
<i>Scaphoideus</i>	sp.	Deltocephalinae	<i>Scaphoideus</i>	sp.
<i>Thamnotettix</i>	<i>brittoni</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Idiodonus</i>	<i>kennicotti</i>

<i>Thamnotettix</i>	<i>nigrifrons</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Graminella</i>	<i>nigrifrons</i>
<i>Thamnotettix</i>	<i>smithi</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Cicadula</i>	<i>smithi</i>
<i>Xestocephalus</i>	<i>brunneus</i>	Deltocephalinae	<i>Xestocephalus</i>	<i>brunneus</i>
<i>Idiocerus</i>	<i>provancheri</i>	Eurymelinae	<i>Balcanocerus</i>	<i>provancheri</i>
<i>Oncopsis</i>	<i>nigrinasi</i>	Eurymelinae	<i>Oncopsis</i>	<i>nigrinasi</i>
		Evacanthinae	<i>Pagaronia</i>	<i>minor</i>
<i>Agallia</i>	<i>novella</i>	Megophthalminae	<i>Agalliopsis</i>	<i>novella</i>
<i>Agallia</i>	<i>quadripunctata</i>	Megophthalminae	<i>Agallia</i>	<i>quadripunctata</i>
<i>Agallia</i>	<i>sanguinolenta</i>	Megophthalminae	<i>Ceratagallia</i>	<i>sanguinolenta</i>
<i>Empoa</i>	<i>commisuralis</i>	Typhlocybinae	<i>Edwardsiana</i>	<i>commisuralis</i>
<i>Empoa</i>	<i>rosae</i>	Typhlocybinae	<i>Edwardsiana</i>	<i>rosae</i>
<i>Empoasca</i>	<i>fabae</i>	Typhlocybinae	<i>Empoasca</i>	<i>fabae</i>
<i>Empoasca</i>	<i>flavescens</i>	Typhlocybinae	<i>Edwardsiana</i>	<i>flavescens</i>
<i>Empoasca</i>	<i>obtusa</i>	Typhlocybinae	<i>Kybos</i>	<i>obtusa</i>
<i>Erythroneura</i>	<i>comes</i>	Typhlocybinae	<i>Erythroneura</i>	<i>comes</i>
<i>Erythroneura</i>	<i>tecta</i>	Typhlocybinae	<i>Rossmoneura</i>	<i>tecta</i>
<i>Erythroneura</i>	<i>trifasciata</i>	Typhlocybinae	<i>Hymetta</i>	<i>trifasciata</i>
<i>Typhlocyba</i>	sp.	Typhlocybinae	<i>Typhlocyba</i>	sp.
Total Species: 55			Total Species: 56	

Table 2. A list of the 20 collecting locations and the total number of leafhoppers collected at each

Location	NBI Plot?	Leafhoppers Collected	Date(s) Inventoried	Latitude	Longitude
20 Vesper Lane	N	2	7/12/2018	41.273527	-70.102242
Almanack Pond Road 1	N	39	7/15/2018	41.293848	-70.008375
Almanack Pond Road 2	N	23	7/15/2018	41.288362	-70.005915
Altar Rock Road	Y	19	7/13/2018	41.286962	-70.030527
Coskata	Y	30	7/12/2018	41.346452	-70.015683
Eel Point 2	Y	45	7/14/2018	41.292857	-70.195535
Folgers Marsh South	Y	71	7/15/2018	41.290276	-70.042614
Loring	Y	55	7/14/2018	41.290310	-70.172843
Madequecham	Y	219	7/13/2018	41.261537	-70.039511
Mass. Audubon	Y	41	7/13/2018	41.276339	-69.990062
Nantucket State Forest	N	88	7/15/2018	41.261159	-70.080696
Norwood Farm	N	61	7/15/2018	41.289510	-70.022092
Pout Ponds	Y	61	7/13/2018	41.276577	-70.046145
SHCP	Y	134	7/14/2018	41.250737	-70.120845
Sheep Pond	Y	114	7/14/2018	41.266121	-70.178517
South Pasture	Y	54	7/13/2018	41.261537	-70.039511
Squam Swamp	Y	27	7/13/2018	41.319129	-70.003536
The Creeks	Y	20	7/14/2018	41.277358	-70.090499
Trotts Swamp	Y	72	7/14/2018	41.276172	-70.141108
U. Mass. Field Station	N	37	7/12–13/2018	41.294409	-70.039949

Table 3. A preliminary list of leafhopper (Cicadellidae) taxa identified thus far from 8 collecting locations on Nantucket. Taxa in bold represent new additions to the Nantucket leafhopper list.

Subfamily	Tribe	Genus
Aphrodinae		<i>Aphrodes</i>
Cicadellinae	Cicadellini	<i>Graphocephala</i>
Cicadellinae	Cicadellini	<i>Neokolla</i>
Deltocephalinae	Athysanini	<i>Eutettix</i>
Deltocephalinae	Athysanini	<i>Orientus</i>
Deltocephalinae	Deltacephalini	<i>Planicephalus</i>
Deltocephalinae	Scaphytopiini	<i>Scaphytopius</i>
Iassinae	Gyponini	<i>Gyponana</i>
Typhlocybinae	Alebrini	<i>Alebra</i>
Typhlocybinae	Typhlocybini	<i>Empoa</i>